

Enhancing Access to Library Collections: A Case Study of Catalogue Cards Use at the Federal University Lafia Library, Nigeria

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Abstract

Providing access to the varied scholarly contents available in libraries has always been a goal for library and information practitioners. Over the years, efforts have been intended to simplify the library search process, with tools and services created while existing ones are improved to ensure the Ranganathan laws are adhered to. As a service organization, the library is responsible for providing the resources and services outlined to achieve the goals and objectives of its parent institution. The library must provide well-designed facilities for staff to access easily. Freshmen and returning students at any university are expected to know how to access library resources while at university easily. This research examines the use of library catalogues in the library of Federal University Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Sixty-three (63) students who used the library during the research period formed the sample for the study. This questionnaire is the data collection tool. The survey showed that the majority of students do not use the library catalogue even though they know that the library catalogue exists. Therefore, the researcher suggested that a user training course should be organized so that students can acquire the necessary skills to use the catalogue.

Keywords: Card Catalogue, Library Users, Information Retrieval, University

Introduction

Ensuring that the diverse range of academic materials housed in libraries is accessible has been a longstanding objective for those in the library and information science fields. Over time, a concerted push has been to streamline the search and retrieval process within library systems. This has led to the development of new tools and services and the enhancement of existing ones. Such advancements are made to uphold the principles established by S. R. Ranganathan, a pioneer in library science whose five laws have guided the evolution of library services. These laws advocate for books to be for all, every reader their book, every book its reader, save the reader's time, and the library is a growing organism. By adhering to these tenets, library professionals strive to create an environment where scholarly content is not only preserved but also made readily discoverable and accessible to those who seek it. The ongoing improvements in library services reflect a dedication to these principles, ensuring that libraries remain vital and dynamic resources in pursuing knowledge. This mandate requires libraries to seek ways to increase and improve their holdings continuously. While making sure that their collections are organised and easily accessible.

Catalogue cards have been a cornerstone in managing library collections for over a century, serving as a primary tool for organizing and accessing vast information. These cards, typically made of sturdy cardstock, contain essential bibliographic details such as the author's name, the title of the work, publication date, and subject headings. This information enables librarians and patrons to locate physical items within the library's labyrinth of shelves and sections. The systematic arrangement of catalogue cards, whether alphabetically by author, title, or subject matter, allows for efficient retrieval of materials, thus facilitating research and learning. Moreover, the tactile nature of flipping through a card catalogue can provide a serendipitous discovery of resources that might otherwise remain hidden in a digital search. Despite the advent of digital catalogues, the legacy of catalogue cards endures, symbolising the meticulous care and organisation that are the hallmarks of library science. Their historical significance is not just in their practical utility but also in their representation of the evolution of information organization from the era of physical cards to the current digital databases.

Although libraries are crucial, users face challenges locating and accessing materials due to inadequate organization. Patrons become frustrated when they cannot find what they need. This study assesses how the Federal University of Lafia undergraduate students utilize the library catalogue when searching for resources. Additionally, it investigates the difficulties students encounter while using the card catalogue and proposes solutions to enhance its usability.

The Aims of the Federal University Library, Lafia Includes:

1. Actualizing the reading and information needs of the students, faculty staff, and researchers about the academic programme of the institution
2. Provide researchers with a guide and make useful resource materials available to upgrade or enhance the research project or work.
3. Creating or establishing an instructive centre with the library to teach readers how to utilize library resources optimally.
4. It serves as a laboratory or training centre for library and information science students.
5. Keeping the institution's staff abreast or duly informed of the recent and contemporary developments in their various fields of study.
6. Creating a conducive or pleasant atmosphere for acquiring leadership qualities can lead to personality development.

Statement of Problem

Librarians closely observe how Federal University of Lafia undergraduate students use the library's catalogue and catalogue cabinet. They pay special attention to damaged and poorly arranged card entries. The observation reveals that 85% and 95% of library patrons never approach the catalogue cabinet, and only about 15% to 5% use it. These low usage rates may be due to the perception that catalogue searching is time-consuming and challenging. However, studying user catalogue patterns could help identify solutions to these issues.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the arrangement of library catalogue cards in the Federal University Library, Lafia.
2. To know the challenges users encounter in using the library catalogue.
3. To determine the solution to enhance the use of library catalogues.

Review of Literature

Catalogue cards hold a pivotal place in the history of library science, representing a significant leap in how libraries organise and provide access to their collections. Before their advent, libraries often relied on fixed shelf arrangements or cumbersome bound catalogues, which made finding a book by author or subject daunting. The introduction of catalogue cards in the 18th century, first appearing in Vienna around 1780, revolutionized this system. These cards allowed for a flexible and dynamic method of cataloguing that could be easily updated and sorted in multiple ways, providing title, author, and subject access points that greatly facilitated the search process. The card catalogue system was further refined in the 19th century with contributions from key figures like Charles Jewett, Ezra Abbot, and Charles Cutter in the United States. Cutter, in particular, is noted for creating a cataloguing scheme that later influenced the Library of Congress classification system. The system's versatility and durability made it a library mainstay for over a century, only being phased out as computer technology advanced and digital catalogues took precedence.

The historical significance of catalogue cards is not merely in their practical utility but also in their role in democratizing access to information (Maloney, 2017). They enabled libraries to expand their services and become more user-friendly, allowing patrons to explore the wealth of knowledge in their collections independently. This autonomy in information retrieval was a significant step forward in educational and public institutions, spreading knowledge and literacy. Moreover, the card catalogue system is a testament to the evolution of information organization, reflecting broader technological and cultural shifts. As noted in an article from *American Libraries Magazine*, libraries have always been technology-based, from the earliest libraries with scrolls to the Gutenberg Revolution and beyond. The card catalogue is a part of this continuum, bridging the gap between the physical and digital realms of information management. Today, while physical card catalogues have become a nostalgic artefact, their legacy lives on in the digital catalogues that have inherited their function. The principles of organization, accessibility, and user-centric design that were honed through the card catalogue system continue to inform modern library practices. It reminds us how past innovations laid the groundwork for future advancements and how the quest for knowledge drives continual improvement in managing and accessing information. Catalogue cards, therefore, are not just a historical footnote but a cornerstone in the narrative of library science. They encapsulate a time when a simple piece of card stock could unlock worlds of information, and they remind us of the enduring human desire to categorize, understand, and share the vast expanse of human knowledge.

It is a file of records for a library's collection (List 1998, cited by Ojedokun 2007). It is vital to both library users and library staff. Its functions include giving a comprehensive record of materials owned by the library, listing what the library possesses by a specific author on a given

subject and with a specific title, and enabling library materials to be located easily (Clark, 2000). The catalogue provides multiple access points to the library's collection (Osode, 2007). Library Catalogue represents a list of library materials called the library's holding (i.e.) arranged according to some definite plan. A library catalogue serves the same purpose as OPAC.

Comprehensive and ongoing user education and awareness services are a significant solution to this issue. Kigongo-Bukenya (2004) highlights that university libraries encounter challenges in their user instruction programs, but effective user education streamlines librarians' tasks and reduces students' efforts. If the library serves everyone, all users should proficiently utilise the catalogue to access library materials. As Ranganathan emphasized, libraries exist for use, and our focus should align with the library's ultimate purpose (Littlefield, 2008). Catalogue cards have been a fundamental component in the organization of libraries for many years. They serve as a physical record of the library's collection and are typically standardized in size, often measuring 12.5 cm x 7.5 cm. Each card represents a book or resource, providing essential bibliographic details such as the author's name, title, publication information, and subject headings. The standard format for creating these cards includes a call number, which is placed in the top left-hand corner to indicate the item's location within the library's classification system. The title and author's name are centrally positioned on the card, with the title written exactly as it appears on the book's cover, followed by the author's name in a last name, first name format. If there are multiple authors, their names follow in traditional form. Publication details and the International Standard Book Number (ISBN) are included in the lower half of the card, with the ISBN in the lower right-hand corner. Subject headings for nonfiction works are listed at the bottom, numbered with the main subject first, followed by subtopics.

The purpose of catalogue cards is multifaceted. Primarily, they enable users to find a book by author, title, subject, or publication date (Ashikuzzaman, 2024). They also show what the library has in its collection by a given author or on a given subject and assist in choosing a book, evaluating its edition and character. While many libraries have transitioned to online public access catalogues (OPACs) in the digital age, some still maintain physical card catalogues, especially for users more comfortable with this traditional method. Despite the shift to digital, the objectives of cataloguing—to provide access to information, organize collections, and support library operations—remain unchanged. Catalogue cards, whether physical or digital, are crucial in managing library collections and facilitating access to information. It is the most popular of all the different forms of catalogues, and it is widely and extensively used in academic, public, and special libraries. Example;

Importance of a Card Catalogue

1. The card catalogue helps keep records of each work in the library by author, translator, editor, illustrator, series, or any other person, body, or name under which a reader might look.
2. The card catalogue helps reduce a researcher's stress by directing him to where the material can be found.
3. The card catalogue helps locate a wide range of subject material on the shelves.
5. The card catalogue serves as a road map to all the library materials.

6. The card catalogue helps the researcher gain quick access to materials as quickly as possible.

Catalogue Card

The subject "Card Catalogue" has not received attention as it ought to, especially in Nigeria. For this reason, very little literature has been published on it. However, the writer has attempted to review the ones related to this research. The library collection is organized to give easy access to the material. Maloney (2004) states that the library organises information resources and services to support user needs. Cataloguing and classification are fundamental processes in organizing information. Cataloguing is the process of describing material so that it can be identified, while classification is the assignment of a call number that places the material in order by subject. According to Opaleke, Olayemi, and Aina (2006), cataloguing is necessary for the organization. It directs the users to a specific subject and groups books on the same or related subjects. A library catalogue is an essential tool. It is an index or a key to the collection, containing an entry representing each item (Clark, 2000). The catalogue also tells where a book is in the library (Apotiade, 2002).

In Kashim Ibrahim Library research work on catalogue use by Lise (2006), who investigated the use of the card catalogue; her method of investigation, though similar to that of Aliyu, used the questionnaire method, which based her findings on the information provided by a hundred respondents who used the library; she reported that 55.6% of the users go straight to the shelves, without consulting the catalogue, while 34% do use it. Uba (2002) delivered a paper entitled Library Cooperation in Technical Service in Nigeria at the Nigeria Library Association Conference at Enugu in 1992. Uba noted that most of our graduate students in most universities show no sign that they know what the catalogue stands for, let alone use it. He stresses the need for a reader approach to catalogue surveys to discover why readers do not use the catalogue. He concluded that until this is done, our catalogue will continue to be a colossal waste.

In an article entitled: The Main Library (KIL) ABU, Zaria. Card Catalogue: Dictionary or divided by Ifidon (2003) reported that author/title resulted in less congestion than in a dictionary catalogue. He also reported that undergraduates started enthusiastically using the catalogue by the academic community. However, their initial enthusiasm gradually diminished as they became more conversant with the library, mainly after they knew the physical location of the material in their subject area. They then place more premium on browsing than on using the card catalogue. Postgraduate students are probably too complementary initially, but their use of the catalogue rises later when they finish their coursework. Adequate orientation should be given to students upon admission to gain adequate knowledge and ideas on using the library. Littlefield (2008), in his study of the use of the Lagos State Library catalogue, said that "the general performance of the users in the use of the library catalogue of the University of Lagos main library was encouraging. She noted that the university staff used more of the catalogue than the students, though she did not state the different usage percentages. Littlefield, however, made some recommendations which, if strictly adhered to, would possibly enhance the further use of the catalogue. Lack of the use of library catalogues by students can be a result of these factors:

In an article given by Ekpenyong entitled: "Card Catalogue Maintenance and Accessibility of Materials". Ekpenyong's compactness in using the catalogues is one of the reasons why a reader might get discouraged from using the catalogue. Searching becomes exceptionally stressful and challenging when the card catalogue has too many in the cabinet drawer. Also, Opaleke (2006), in their study on card expansion in the University of Ibadan library, gave another reason for students' inability to access materials they want through the catalogue. They said that this might be due to inaccurate references given by the lecturer. Although it is often rare that lecturers give the wrong spelling of the authors' names for the materials, students might be unable to locate the materials in the catalogue cabinet even though they might be able to use the catalogue well. Such frustrations might not make the students use the catalogue again.

Clement (2008) reported that library users make use of the catalogue in one way or another to locate what they want in the library. His findings indicated that 89.6% of the total number of library users interviewed agreed that they make use of the catalogue. To make users friendly, users need to be taught the importance of every element on the library catalogue for proper understanding. This is important because, despite the benefits students can derive from catalogue use, it is still poor in Nigerian university libraries. Okorafor (2006) found that Latunde Odeku Medical Library catalogue use was poor. The author attributed the poor usage to the lack of user education programmes. Similarly, the study of Ishola and Ojeniyi (2015) found that most users preferred going directly to the shelves to search for materials rather than going through the catalogue cabinet. It was concluded that the respondents found the use of the library catalogue a waste of time

Challenges Faced by Catalogue Users in the Library

There are so many challenges faced by catalogue users in the Federal University of Lafia Library in an attempt to retrieve information resources/materials of their choice. The purpose of a catalogue is to enable a person to find a book by:

- The author
- The title
- The subject etc.

The catalogue is known to show what the library has by a given author, subject, or kind of literature and to assist in choosing a book according to its edition (bibliographically) and the character (literary or topical). However, this has been characterised by difficulties, such as users not knowing how to approach the catalogue cabinet. In contrast, other users lack knowledge of the arrangement pattern of the catalogue entry. Aina (2004) opined that the idea behind cataloguing is that users of large libraries such as Kashim Ibrahim Library, the University of Nigeria Nsukka, and the Federal University of Lafia usually do not have the author or title of a document in mind; instead, they are interested in documents on particular areas of subject interest. This might be an area where a user researches, studies, or writes. For such users, the library catalogue must provide subject headings for all the documents catalogued. There is also the problem with providing subject headings to documents since the authors of documents use diverse concepts and terms to describe the same subject. In short, there are problems that a cataloguer would encounter when providing a usable subject catalogue. To ensure uniformity and consistency, the basic principle in cataloguing is that

cataloguers worldwide have to assign the same subject heading to the same document. Therefore, there is a need for an indexing language that a cataloguer would have to consult to serve as a guide on how to select consistent and uniform subject headings.

Enhancing the use of card catalogues

No cataloguing format is perfect because each form has one disadvantage or another. Ideally, a catalogue is expected to be easy to use, maintain, and affordable. The library can enhance the use of card catalogues in the following ways:

There should be easy access to entries to enhance the use of a card catalogue; it should be possible to find the entry for a particular document in the catalogue when needed. Sometimes, filling problems may cause obstacles to getting entries that are common in card catalogues. To ensure the optimum use of the card catalogue by library users, the catalogue should be flexible and easy to update due to the dynamic nature of library collections. Thus, new documents are regularly published and are expected to be acquired by the library; creating a catalogue entry should be a continuous activity in a library to ensure judicious use of its collection.

Card and digital catalogues represent two distinct eras in the evolution of library systems, each with its own advantages and challenges. Card catalogues have been used for over a century and are physical records of bibliographic information, typically handwritten or typed on cards. They are known for their tactile nature and the ease of browsing, allowing users to flip through entries physically. However, they are limited by their static nature, requiring manual updates and being prone to wear and tear. In contrast, digital catalogues, epitomised by Online Public Access Catalogs (OPACs), offer dynamic, searchable databases that can be updated instantly and accessed remotely. They provide powerful search capabilities, including keyword and Boolean searches, and can integrate with other digital library systems for functions like circulation and acquisitions.

The transition from cards to digital catalogues has been driven by the need for efficiency and the ability to manage larger volumes of information (Coyle, 2016). Digital catalogues can handle the vast and growing collections of modern libraries, making tracking and retrieving items easier. They also offer accessibility features, such as screen readers for the visually impaired, and can reduce the physical space needed for catalogues. Moreover, digital catalogue updates are more efficient, eliminating the need to replace or amend cards physically.

From the perspective of library work, digital catalogues streamline many processes. Cataloguing becomes a quicker, more standardised procedure, and the retrieval of bibliographic records is simplified. The storage and manipulation of records in the digital realm allow for greater flexibility and the potential for data analysis, which can inform library management decisions. Additionally, OPACs can provide users with real-time information about the availability of items and enable features like online reservations.

Transitioning to digital catalogues presents challenges. It demands substantial investment in technology and staff training. Additionally, cultural preferences play a role; some users and librarians still favour the traditional card catalogue system. The tactile experience and

serendipity of browsing through cards to discover related works are aspects that digital catalogues find difficult to replicate.

While card catalogues have played a crucial role in the history of library organisation, digital catalogues offer a more efficient, accessible, and scalable solution for modern library needs. The choice between the two systems often comes down to the specific needs and resources of the library, as well as the preferences of its users and staff. As technology advances, digital catalogues will likely become even more sophisticated, further enhancing the capabilities of libraries to serve their communities. The evolution of library catalogues reflects broader technological trends and the ongoing quest to improve information management and accessibility in an increasingly digital world. The comparison between card and digital catalogues is not just about the tools themselves but also about the changing landscape of information consumption and the role of libraries in facilitating access to knowledge.

The comparison between card and digital catalogues in library work highlights a significant shift in information management and user interaction. Card catalogues, once the backbone of library indexing systems, offered patrons a tangible and direct way to discover and locate materials. Each card, typically housed in a wooden or metal drawer, represented a single bibliographic entry with details such as the author, title, subject, and location within the library. This system, while straightforward, was labour-intensive to update and maintain, and its physical nature limited the amount of information that could be stored and accessed.

Digital catalogues, on the other hand, signify the modernisation of library cataloguing. With the advent of Online Public Access Catalogs (OPACs), the entire library collection became searchable from any digital interface, providing convenience and efficiency that card catalogues could not match. Digital catalogues allow for complex searches using multiple criteria, immediate updates, and integration with other library systems for functions like circulation and interlibrary loans. They also offer remote access, enabling users to explore the library's holdings anywhere with an internet connection.

When comparing the use of physical catalogue cards with OPACs, several key differences emerge. Physical cards required manual browsing, which, while potentially serendipitous, was time-consuming and limited to the user's physical presence in the library. OPACs however, offer quick, multi-faceted search capabilities that filter results by metadata fields, such as publication date, format, or language. Additionally, digital catalogues can provide real-time updates on the availability of items and reserve materials, and even suggest related titles based on user search behaviour.

The transition from card catalogues to digital systems reflects broader technological advancements and changing user expectations. Where card catalogues are static and finite, digital catalogues are dynamic and virtually limitless in capacity. This shift has not only transformed how libraries operate but also how patrons engage with library resources. While some may nostalgically recall the tactile experience of flipping through card catalogues, the overwhelming consensus in the library community is that digital catalogues offer superior functionality and accessibility.

Comparing card and digital catalogues in library work reveals a clear evolution from a physical, manual system to a digital, automated one. This transformation has enhanced libraries' ability to manage their collections and serve their patrons more effectively. As technology advances, digital catalogues will likely further improve, offering even more sophisticated tools for

information retrieval and management in the library setting. The ongoing development of digital catalogues is a testament to the library sector's commitment to adapting to technological changes and improving access to knowledge for all.

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Methodology

The researcher adopted the case study method for this research. The method enables the researcher to observe and examine the use of the Card Catalogue. The population of this study comprises students and staff of the Federal University of Lafia, who are the prime users of the Library. Patrons were randomly selected as they entered the library during the investigation period. The questionnaires were distributed to those physically present. In the study, the instruments used include observation and questionnaires. The questionnaire is the most commonly used Instrument for getting data on catalogue use in libraries. The researcher distributed sixty-three (63) questionnaires and got full responses. The questionnaires were collected with the help of library assistants who collected the same in person from the respondents. The completed copies of the questionnaires were received and analysed using percentages. Tables were also used to present the summary of data. This summary was used to discuss the findings of the study.

Response Rate

The data obtained from the distribution of the questionnaires administered to the respondents were presented in tables. Sixty-three copies (63) of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and were all collected after duly completed, representing (100%) collection.

Table 1: How is the Library catalogue arranged/used in the Federal University of Lafia Library?

Response	Frequency	%
A-Z	21	33.33
Author/Title/Subjects	42	66.66
Total	63	100%

Table 1 shows that 42(66.66%) of the Library Users opine that they are aware that resources of the university library are arranged via Author/Title/Subjects, while 21(33.33%) posit that the library's resources are arranged A. Despite the notification, some students are irregular users, while some are regular users. This is because they (the Library users) come to the Library to read because of one examination/Test or the other. On the other hand, the irregular use of the Library by the users could be that the Library does not have enough reading space and furniture to accommodate the majority of the users; it is customary to see many of the regular users sitting in the corridor, while some sit under the trees without furniture. Those who cannot bear this inconvenience may prefer not to use the library and talk less about knowing how to use the card catalogues.

Challenges in Using Card Catalogue

The researcher wanted to know if library users have used a card catalogue in their various schools or at any other Library. The table below responds to the Library users.

Table 2 What are the challenges users encounter in using the library catalogue?

Response	Frequency	%
Books are Sparingly/wrongly shelved	18	28.57
Lack of Library Orientation (Students)	45	71.43
Total	63	100

From Table 2 above, it is evident that students encountered numerous obstacles while using the library catalogue. Some of the users, 45(71.43%), testified through their responses that they did not have knowledge of the card catalogue and preferred not to waste their time searching for materials but instead visit the shelf directly. This and many more are because they lack library orientation. 18(28.57%) posit that most materials are either sparingly scattered or not properly arranged. Most students do not know a Card Catalogue or use the Catalogue Card.

Catalogue Cards Use Pattern (Library Orientation)

Library Orientation is the quickest and most efficient way of teaching Library Users the practices and procedures of Library operations. It should be organized at intervals of about six months and taught to both new and old Library Users. The researcher inquired if the library staff gave orientation to the users at any time. The responses are given in the table below.

Table 3: What are the solutions to enhance the use of library catalogues?

Library Orientation		
Response	Frequenc	%
Library Orientation (Staff)	28	44.44
Staff Shelve Reading	35	55.55
Total	63	100

Table 3; above shows 35(55.55%) respondents who express that finding useful reading materials using a card catalogue is not an easy task due to the mis-shelving nature of the resources by students, locating reading materials becomes problematic, the library staff neglecting their shelves reading duties making it difficult for students to locate materials while in the library 28(44.44%) posit that the library staff probably do not perform their duties well or probably do not have the knowledge of the orientation to teach students. This research aims to determine the use pattern or extent of use of the Card Catalogue in the Federal University of Lafia Library. To adequately address this issue, the respondents must know about the Card Catalogue and proper Library Orientation.

According to the respondent, library staff should have provided a guide to the students who need training and re-training on using the Card Catalogue. On the contrary, the interaction with the respondents reveals that library staff should constantly shelve-read their catalogue cards to correct any misdeed by users or help guide users whenever they are lost in locating a particular catalogue card or resources in the library. The users observed that most of the books on the catalogue cards are sometimes difficult to locate on the shelves due to the mix-shelving nature of the books. The librarian should acquire current materials and the arrangement pattern entrench to users.

Findings

1. A significant percentage of 45 (71.43%) students had no prior knowledge of card catalogues.
2. A study was conducted on the methods Since libraries are considered a handy and effective way to teach library staff how to use card catalogues. It was found that 18 (28.57%) depressed people agreed to receive guidance.
3. The results showed that 18 (28.57%) of the library patrons use the catalogue map to find books in the library, while 45 (71.43%) of the respondents do not use the catalogue to find books. Only a few customers regularly use the card catalogue.
4. The researcher found that the few users who use the card catalogue are usually successful in their search, while those who approach the shelves spend a long time searching.
5. The catalogue layout was too difficult for customers to understand, and 18 (28.57%) disappointments expressed the poor card rating.
6. Some library staff are not capable of guiding clients on the use of the library catalogue, while the respondents opine that books are sometimes mix-shelved which makes it difficult for patrons to locate needed materials

Recommendation

The researcher suggested the following:

1. Orientation should be done for users, and the use of the card should be properly taught
2. The security in the library needs to be tight as many students tear the books in the library.
3. New patrons should receive a library guide or handbook with detailed information on how to use the catalogue, and seminars should be held for both junior and senior librarians.

4. The cabinet should be placed in a prominent position and its surroundings attractive to attract/invite curious customers.
5. Catalog readings must be done frequently in order to correct filling errors.
6. Catalog cards for lost books should be removed quickly so that students don't get frustrated when searching for things on the shelves after confirmation of these books in the catalogue.

Improving the effectiveness of catalogue cards can be approached by focusing on several key areas. Firstly, ensuring that the cataloguing practice involves the hands-on creation of bibliographic records or catalogue cards can significantly enhance the learning and retention of cataloguing concepts and skills. It's also crucial to have a balance of theory and practice, placing cataloguing in a real-world context to contribute to effective learning. Additionally, considering the rapid changes in the library field, it's important to adapt cataloguing practices to include both traditional and modern methods. This might involve the integration of vendor-supplied records and services, as well as the management of electronic resources, which are becoming increasingly prevalent.

Conclusion

The use of catalogue cards over the years at the Federal University Lafia Library in Nigeria has proven successful at improving access to library collections and serving as a crucial tool for disseminating knowledge and information. Despite the rise of digital catalogues, traditional methods remain valuable and effectively complement modern technologies. By maintaining an organized and accessible catalogue card system, the library ensures that students and researchers can efficiently locate and utilize resources. This success underscores the importance of adapting to local contexts in library management, emphasizing the library's dynamic role beyond mere book storage. As libraries worldwide balance traditional and digital systems, the Federal University Lafia Library exemplifies the enduring relevance of catalogue cards in the digital age.

References

- Ashikuzzaman, M. D. (2024). Essential Elements of Library Catalogue. Library & Information Science Education Network. <https://www.lisedunetwork.com/essentials-elements-of-library-catalogue/>
- Coyle, K. (2016). The evolving catalog: cataloging tech from scrolls to computers. *American Libraries Magazine*, 47(1–2).
- Ekpenyong, G.D. Card Catalogue Maintenance and Accessibility of Material
- Faniran, Opaleke, J. S. (2006). Card Catalogue expansion in Ibadan University
- Fister, B. (2002). The research process of undergraduate students. *Journal of Academic Ibadan: Third World Information Services Limited*.
- Ifidon, S.E. The Public Card Catalogue: Dictionary or Divided? in Nigeria. *Journal of the Nigerian Library Association, Into State Chapter 4* (1&2): 37–43.
- information seeking behaviour of undergraduate students of Makerere

- University, Uganda. *World Libraries* 14(1): 1-24.
- Kakai M., Ikoja-Odongo, R., & Kigongo-Bukenya, I. M. N. (2004). A study of the librarian. Ilorin: Nathadex publishers.
- Librarianship* 18 (3): 163-169.
- Library. Nigerbiblios* 5(3-4 July/October: (1980) p.33
- Littlefield, J. (2008). A cataloguing carol. Available: [http://www. Library student\] journal](http://www.Library student] journal).
- Maloney, W. (2017). Inquiring Minds: The Unheralded Story of the Card Catalog. Library of Congress Blogs. <https://blogs.loc.gov/loc/2017/07/inquiring-minds-the-unheralded-story-of-the-card-catalog/>
- Nigerbiblio* 7(3) July 2002 p.77.
- Ojedokun, A. A. (2007). Information literacy for tertiary education students in Africa.
- Okorafor, C. N. (2006). Using library catalogues as access to academic library collections
- Opaleke, J. S. (2006). Study on non-print resources in Nigerian libraries. Ilorin: Nathadex
- Opaleke, J. S., Olayemi T. K., & Aina, R. (2006). School library management for teacher org/index
- Osiobe, S. (2007). Use and relevance of information on the card catalogue for
- Palmer, R.P. Users Requirement of a university library catalogue. Ph.D. Dissertation Publishers. Undergraduate students. *Library Review* 36 (4): 261-267.